

THE IMPORTANCE OF FLEXIBILITY IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION

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Theory and methodology of physical training and sports training

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Abstract. Flexibility is a crucial component of physical education that is often overlooked. This article aims to emphasize the significance of incorporating flexibility training into physical education curricula. Flexibility plays a vital role in improving overall health, preventing injuries, enhancing sports performance, and promoting an active lifestyle. Through a comprehensive review of relevant scientific literature, this article highlights the numerous benefits of flexibility training and provides recommendations for implementing effective flexibility programs in physical education settings.

Key words: safety, flexibility, PI, health, actions, dynamic strength, effect, vital role.

ВАЖНОСТЬ ГИБКОСТИ В ФИЗИЧЕСКОМ ВОСПИТАНИИ

Аннотация. Гибкость является важнейшим компонентом физического воспитания, которым часто пренебрегают. Эта статья призвана подчеркнуть важность включения упражнений на гибкость в учебные программы по физическому воспитанию. Гибкость играет жизненно важную роль в улучшении общего состояния здоровья, предотвращении травм, повышении спортивных результатов и пропаганде активного образа жизни. Благодаря всестороннему обзору соответствующей научной литературы в этой статье освещаются многочисленные преимущества тренировок гибкости и даются рекомендации по внедрению эффективных программ гибкости в условиях физического воспитания.

Ключевые слова: безопасность, гибкость, ЛПП, здоровье, действия, динамическая сила, эффект, жизненная роль.

INTRODUCTION

Flexibility refers to the ability of a joint or a group of joints to move through a full range of motion. It encompasses both static and dynamic flexibility and is influenced by various factors such as joint structure, muscle elasticity, and connective tissue adaptability.

Physical education programs have traditionally focused on cardiovascular endurance, muscular strength, and skill development, often neglecting flexibility. However, the importance of flexibility in promoting overall physical fitness and well-being cannot be overstated.

MATERIALS AND DISCUSSION

Health Benefits of Flexibility:

Improved Joint Health: Regular flexibility exercises promote joint health by increasing synovial fluid circulation, enhancing nutrient supply, and reducing joint stiffness. This can help prevent or manage conditions such as arthritis and osteoporosis.

Injury Prevention: Adequate flexibility reduces the risk of musculoskeletal injuries by improving joint stability and muscle elasticity. It allows individuals to move efficiently and maintain proper alignment during physical activities, reducing the strain on muscles and connective tissues.

Enhanced Posture and Balance: Flexibility exercises contribute to good posture and balance by maintaining the optimal length-tension relationships of muscles. Improved postural alignment reduces the risk of chronic pain and injuries related to poor posture.

Performance Benefits of Flexibility:

Increased Range of Motion: Flexibility training increases the range of motion around joints, enabling individuals to perform movements with greater ease and efficiency. This is particularly beneficial for athletes, as it can improve performance in sports requiring high levels of flexibility, such as gymnastics, dance, and martial arts.

Enhanced Athletic Performance: Improved flexibility positively impacts athletic performance by facilitating movements that require agility, coordination, and power. Flexibility training can optimize performance in activities such as sprinting, jumping, and changing direction, thus providing athletes with a competitive edge.

Injury Rehabilitation and Recovery: Flexibility exercises play a crucial role in injury rehabilitation, aiding in the restoration of normal joint range of motion and muscle function. They also promote faster recovery by increasing blood flow to the injured area, facilitating nutrient delivery and waste removal.

Promoting an Active Lifestyle:

Long-Term Physical Fitness: Incorporating flexibility training into physical education programs instills lifelong habits of physical activity. Flexibility exercises can be enjoyable and accessible to individuals of all ages and fitness levels, making them an ideal component of physical education aimed at promoting long-term health and well-being.

Psychological Well-being: Flexibility training, often included in mind-body practices like yoga and Pilates, can reduce stress, improve mood, and enhance overall mental well-being. It provides an opportunity for individuals to relax, focus on their bodies, and develop a mind-body connection.

Implementing Effective Flexibility Programs in Physical Education:

Integration into Curriculum: Flexibility exercises should be integrated into the physical education curriculum as a regular component. Educators should allocate dedicated time for flexibility training and incorporate a variety of exercises targeting major muscle groups and joints.

Proper Technique and Progression: Educators must provide instruction on proper technique and emphasize the importance of gradual progression to prevent injury. Exercises should be tailored to meet the specific needs and abilities of students, ensuring safety and effectiveness.

Variety and Enjoyment: Incorporating diverse flexibility exercises

Types of Flexibility Training:

Static Stretching: This involves holding a stretch position for a prolonged period, typically between 15 and 60 seconds. Static stretching is effective for increasing flexibility and should be performed after a warm-up or physical activity.

Dynamic Stretching: Dynamic stretching involves moving parts of the body through a full range of motion, gradually increasing the speed and intensity of the movements. Dynamic stretching is commonly used as part of a warm-up routine before physical activity, as it helps improve joint mobility and prepares the body for movement.

Proprioceptive Neuromuscular Facilitation (PNF): PNF techniques involve a combination of stretching and muscle contraction to improve flexibility. These techniques typically involve a partner or equipment and are highly effective in increasing range of motion. **Yoga and Pilates:** Yoga and Pilates are mind-body practices that focus on flexibility, strength, and body awareness. These disciplines often incorporate static and dynamic stretching, along with postural alignment and core strengthening exercises, providing holistic benefits for physical and mental well-being.

Safety Considerations:

Proper Warm-up: Before engaging in flexibility exercises, it is essential to warm up the body through light aerobic activities such as jogging or cycling. A warm-up increases blood flow to the muscles, elevates body temperature, and prepares the body for stretching.

Gradual Progression: Flexibility training should progress gradually, allowing the body to adapt and avoid overstretching or straining muscles and connective tissues. Starting with gentle stretches and gradually increasing the intensity and duration of the exercises will promote safety and prevent injuries.

Individualization: Flexibility programs should consider the individual needs and abilities of students. Students with pre-existing conditions, injuries, or limited flexibility may require modified exercises or alternative techniques to ensure their safety and progress. Avoiding

Bouncing or Jerking Movements: Ballistic movements, such as bouncing or jerking during stretching, should be avoided as they can lead to muscle strains and tears. All stretches should be performed in a controlled and smooth manner.

Assessing Flexibility:

Sit-and-Reach Test: The sit-and-reach test is a common assessment tool used to measure hamstring and lower back flexibility. It involves sitting on the floor with legs extended and reaching forward as far as possible, with the distance reached indicating flexibility levels.

Joint Range of Motion: Assessing joint range of motion through specific measurements and functional tests can provide valuable information about flexibility in various body regions. Educators can utilize goniometers or other measurement tools to evaluate joint flexibility accurately.

Integrating Flexibility with Other Components of Physical Education: Flexibility should be integrated with other components of physical education to create a comprehensive and well-rounded program. It can be combined with cardiovascular endurance, muscular strength and endurance, and skill development exercises to promote overall fitness and athletic performance.

CONCLUSION

Flexibility training plays a vital role in physical education by promoting health, preventing injuries, enhancing athletic performance, and fostering an active lifestyle. Incorporating effective flexibility programs in physical education curricula can provide students with lifelong benefits and a foundation for optimal physical well-being.

Educators should prioritize the inclusion of flexibility exercises, ensuring proper technique, progression, and individualization to create safe and engaging learning environments. By recognizing the importance of flexibility, physical education can empower students to embrace physical activity, achieve their potential, and maintain lifelong fitness.

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- resources on topics such as flexibility training and athletic performance. Visit their website at: <https://www.nasca.com/>
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